

Tris(bipyridyl)- and tris(phenanthroline)nickel(II) *O,O*-alkylene dithiophosphates

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The paramagnetic octahedral *O,O*-alkylenedithiophosphate derivatives of the general formula, $[\text{Ni}(\text{bipy}/\text{phen.})_3](\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{O})_2\text{G})_2$ (where $\text{G}(\text{OH})_2 = 2,3\text{-dimethylbutane-2,3-diol}$, butane-2,3-diol and $2\text{-methylpentane-2,4-diol}$) have been synthesized by the reaction of bis(*O,O*-alkylene dithiophosphato)nickel(II) with 2,2'-bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline in 1 : 3 molar ratio. IR and electronic spectra along with magnetic data indicate six-coordinated octahedral geometry.

Alkylene dithiophosphates of nickel, palladium and platinum have been the thrust area of our research¹⁻⁵. Synthesis of nickel(II)-alkylene dithiophosphates with bipyridyl and phenanthroline has been reported³. The attempt to prepare 1 : 2 adducts results in the formation of a mixture of 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 adducts. However, the reaction of nickel (II)-alkylene dithiophosphates with bipyridyl and phenanthroline in 1 : 3 molar ratio results in the formation of the complexes in which all the four sulfur atoms of the dithiophosphates moieties come out of the coordination sphere and Ni^{II} is surrounded by six nitrogen atoms. It shows the stronger chelation power of heterocyclic tertiary amine in comparison to the dithiophosphate moieties.

Results and Discussion

Tris(bipyridyl)- and tris(phenanthroline)nickel(II)-*O,O*-alkylene dithiophosphates have been prepared by the reaction of bis(*O,O*-alkylene dithiophosphato)nickel(II) with 2,2'-bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline in 1 : 3 molar ratio in dichloromethane :

Dropwise addition of a solution of 2,2'-bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline in dichloromethane to a solution of bis(alkylene dithiophosphato)nickel(II) in the same solvent resulted in a gradual change in the colour of the solution from violet to green and then pink. It therefore appears that

1 : 1 adduct was formed initially which in the presence of excess base reacted further to give the pink 1 : 3 complex.

These derivatives are dull or shining pink powder or semi-crystalline solids which melts above 290°, with a change in colour to green at around 170°; this indicates the intermediate formation of 1 : 1 adduct. These complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in halocarbons (CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂). Like open-chain dialkyl dithiophosphates⁶, the cyclic bis(*O,O*-alkylene dithiophosphato)nickel(II) complexes reacted with bipyridyl and phenanthroline in 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 molar ratio, when the reactants were taken in appropriate quantities. The reaction in 1 : 2 molar ratio interestingly resulted in the formation of a mixture of 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 adducts.

It appears quite reasonable that these tri-complexes, should be ionic in nature but conductivity measurements indicate that these are non-conducting in chloroform and dichloromethane. This may be either due to bulky nature of these ions which are not mobile or it remains undissociated in solution. An attempt was made to test the ionic nature of these complexes by simple chemical test. Treatment of tris(bipyridyl)nickel(II)-2,3-butylene dithiophosphate in dichloromethane with aqueous AgNO₃ solution gave a white precipitate of silver butylene dithiophosphate. However, the uncomplexed bis(2,3-butylene dithiophosphato)nickel(II) also showed a similar replacement reaction with silver nitrate and thus no useful information could be obtained.

IR spectra of these compounds exhibit bands at 1150–1030 and 890–800 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to (P)–O–C and P–O–(C) stretching vibrations, respectively⁷. The

bands at 930–900 cm^{-1} may be assigned to dioxaphospholane and dioxaphosphorinane ring vibrations^{8,9}. A strong band at 690–670 cm^{-1} has been ascribed to $\nu_{\text{P-S}}$. The bands at 630–495 cm^{-1} are attributed to P–S sym. and asym. vibrations. The bands at 340–305 cm^{-1} are due to Ni–S vibrations. Due to a number of ring vibrations of bipyridyl and phenanthroline molecule, it was not possible to assign Ni–N band.

³¹P NMR spectra of only one representative compound, tris(phen.)nickel(II) tetramethylethylene dithiophosphate could be recorded. ³¹P chemical shift value in chloroform is δ 122 ppm, which is same as in the case of 1 : 1 adduct of phenanthroline with bis(tetramethylethylenedithiophosphato)nickel(II)³.

Magnetic moments of tris(bipyridyl)- and tris(phenanthroline)-*O,O*-alkylenedithiophosphates in general fall in the range 3.08–3.38 B.M., indicating the presence of two unpaired electrons, expected for octahedral geometry of these complexes. However, tris(bipy.)-2,3-butylenedithiophosphate of nickel(II) shows magnetic moment of 2.52 B.M. at room temperature which is below the spin-only value, which indicates the presence of antiferromagnetism¹⁰. However, the definite information can only be obtained by low temperature magnetic measurements. The phenomenon of antiferromagnetism indicates associated nature of molecules which could plausibly be *trans* as illustrated in Fig. 1. On the other extreme, the value of magnetic moments of tris(phen.)tetramethylethylenedithiophosphates of nickel(II) at room temperature is 4.25 B.M., which is higher than the expected value for octahedral geometry. This is analogous to the 1 : 1 bipyridyl adducts of bis(2,3-butylenedithiophosphato)nickel(II) and it can be assigned due to tetragonal geometry¹¹.

Fig. 1

The electronic spectral data of all the compounds (620–650, 1080–1110 nm) are typical of octahedral nickel(II) complexes^{3,12}.

The above spectral and magnetic studies indicate six-coordinated geometry of the above compounds.

Experimental

O,O-Alkylene dithiophosphates of nickel(II) were prepared by the reported method².

Synthesis of tris(bipy.) and tris(phen.)nickel(II)-O,O-alkylene dithiophosphates :

Reaction of bis(hexylene dithiophosphato)nickel(II) with phenanthroline in 1 : 3 molar ratio : A solution of 1,10-phenanthroline (1.75 g) in dichloromethane was added dropwise to a solution of bis(hexylene dithiophosphato)nickel(II) (1.33 g) in the same solvent and the mixture was heated for a few minutes. Acetone (~10–15 ml) was then added to it and the reaction mixture was kept at 0°. The resulting pink crystals of tris(phenanthroline)nickel(II) hexylene dithiophosphates (2.26 g) were washed with acetone and dried under vacuum, yields 86–89%.

Reaction of bis(tetramethylethylene dithiophosphato)nickel(II) with bipyridyl in 1 : 3 molar ratio : To a slurry of bis(tetramethylethylene dithiophosphato)nickel(II) in dichloromethane (1.40 g), a solution of bipyridyl (1.39 g) in the same solvent was added slowly. The resulting clear solution first turned violet to green and ultimately to pink on complete addition of bipyridyl. The reaction mixture was heated for a few minutes and after addition of acetone kept at room temperature and ultimately at 0°. The pink crystals of tris(bipy.)nickel(II)tetramethylethylene dithiophosphate that separated out was washed with acetone and dried under vacuum, yields 77–95%.

All complexes gave satisfactory Ni and S analyses.

IR spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, ³¹P NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker 500 MHz spectrometer using H₃PO₄ as an external standard and electronic spectra (CH₂Cl₂) on a Cary 17-D spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was determined by the Faraday method. Diamagnetic corrections were calculated from Pascal's constant.

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